

FAILURE UNDER MULTIAXIAL STRESSES OF COMPONENT MATERIALS FOR FIBER COMPOSITE SANDWICH CONSTRUCTION

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The benefits of reducing the weight of ships and other marine vessels has led to major efforts in exploiting sandwich construction for primary load-bearing structures. While this approach has had a long history of use in aerospace applications, it is relatively new to large-scale marine structures. One key to the success of utilizing fiber composite materials for sandwich construction is affordability, which is most strongly related to processing and raw material costs. The goal is to achieve aerospace performance, but at a much reduced cost. Both cost and weight savings can also be optimized through the most efficient use of the materials. To achieve efficient use of materials in structural design, it is critical that physically based and proven constitutive and failure models be developed for use in numerical simulations. Otherwise, unnecessarily large safety factors are imposed through overcompensated designs.

The goal of this work was to characterize the failure of both fiber composite skin and porous core materials under multiaxial stresses for ongoing evaluation of existing three-dimensional failure models. Two methods for producing a known state of multiaxial stress were developed. A high-pressure test system, which allows uniaxial testing under superimposed hydrostatic pressure up to 0.7 GPa, was developed specifically for testing fiber composite materials. Failure under a biaxial stress state of shear plus tension or compression was examined using hollow cylindrical specimens in a tension/torsion hydraulic test machine.

The failure of materials under superimposed hydrostatic pressure, while not necessarily directly related to stresses experienced in applications, is a discriminating means to evaluate failure theories for reinforced and pure polymeric materials, which are known to exhibit pressure-dependent behavior. For example, the predicted effects of pressure on the fiber-direction failure of a lamina are shown in Figure 1 for some common failure theories. Clearly there are significant differences in both the predicted magnitudes and trends, which

allows meaningful assessments of theories against experimental results. Our results for carbon fiber composites indicate that the Christensen and Feng models adequately predict the effect of pressure on fiber-direction compression strength. Significant changes in matrix-dominated lamina failure due to superimposed pressure were also observed. Comparisons of these effects for carbon and glass fiber composites based on both thermosetting and thermoplastic matrix materials will be summarized and compared with theoretical predictions.

Fig. 1: Predicted fiber-direction strengths of a lamina under superimposed pressure.

Core materials for sandwich structures are primarily subjected to shear and through-thickness compression. Due to the geometric constraints imposed by the skin, compression is essentially uniaxial strain, which yields a combined stress state having a significant hydrostatic component. For isotropic core materials, such as open- and closed-cell foams and syntactics, simple failure criteria may apply. However, the normally large disparity between tensile and compressive strengths exhibited by porous materials suggests a strong dependence of failure on pressure. Furthermore, unlike most solid media, porous materials can undergo failure due to pure hydrostatic compression at relatively low levels. Failure models must capture these pressure effects.

Experimental results for failure of typical foam core materials under combined shear and normal stresses, as well as under pure hydrostatic pressure, will be presented. The ability of proposed pressure-dependent failure models for isotropic materials to predict the observed failure envelopes will be described.